

Water regime	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water requirement (mm)	Water use efficiency (kg grain/ha-mm)
Continuous submergence (5 cm water)	5.5	1530	3.60
5 cm water 2 DADPW ^b	5.2	935	5.41
5 cm water 3 DADPW	4.6	850	5.37
5 cm water 4 DADPW	4.1	765	5.36
5 cm water 5 DADPW	3.4	680	4.95
LSD (0.05)	0.7	-	-

*Mean of 2 yr. ^bDADPW = d after disappearance of ponded water.

Farming systems

Establishing rainfed no-till winter crops under NPK fertilization after transplanted wet rice

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We studied the feasibility of establishing crops after transplanted wet rice during winter without tilling and using only residual moisture.

The field experiment was laid out in a factorial randomized block design, replicated four times, and conducted during winter seasons (1990-91 and 1991-92) at the University Farm, Kalyani, West Bengal, India. Experimental soil was a low-lying alluvial with 0.62% organic C, 0.06% total N, 7.9 kg available P/ha, 151.1 kg available K/ha, and pH 6.8.

Effect of different NPK fertilizer levels on seed and stover yields (t/ha) of rainfed winter crops of mustard, grasspea, lentil, and linseed after transplanted wet rice (IR36). West Bengal, India, 1990-92.

Rainfed winter crop	NPK fertilizer							
	None		Recommended dose		1.5 × recommended dose		Mean	
	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover
Mustard	0.5	2.0	0.7	3.0	1.5	4.2	0.9	3.2
Grasspea	1.0	4.0	1.1	4.9	0.8	4.4	1.0	4.4
Lentil	1.2	4.7	1.3	4.0	1.2	3.7	1.2	4.1
Linseed	0.4	1.3	0.7	1.6	0.8	1.8	0.6	1.5
Mean	0.8	3.0	1.0	3.4	1.1	3.5	0.9	3.3
	Fertilizer (F)		Crops (C)		F × C			
	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover	Seed	Stover
LSD (0.05)			0.3	ns ^a	0.4	0.7	0.5	1.2

^ans = not significant.

Varietal diffusion in a rice farming system

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We studied the diffusion pattern of rice varieties developed through a farming systems research and extension (FSR/E) program. Farmers in the southern Sri Lankan district of Matara are confronted with strong soil acidification (pH 3.5-4.0) during the dry season (DS) and excess water during the wet season (WS).

During the technology generation stage of the FSR/E program, rice varieties were screened for tolerance for soil acidification and submergence. Varieties BW272-3 and At85-1 were selected. Both have growth duration of 3 1/2 mo. Based on experimental and on-farm trial results, BW272-3 was introduced in the district in 1988 DS and At85-1 in 1990 DS. See figure for diffusion trends.

BW272-3 had medium tolerance for acidic soils and submerged condition. It exhibited medium resistance to thrips (*Thrips oryzae*) and sheath blight (ShB) (*Corticium sasakii*) and is 95-100 cm tall. The field's microenvironment did not favor the spread of common insect pests and diseases. Unfavorable characteristics included low resistance to brown planthopper (*Nilaparvata lugens* Stål), high grain shattering, lower grain weight (21-22 g/1,000 seeds), and white pericarp.

BW272-3 was considered to be a moderately appropriate variety for the target area. Farmers adopted this variety at first, but later responded to the low grain weight and higher farmgate price of red-pericarped varieties. The diffusion curve of BW272-3 shows a declining adoption trend two seasons after it was introduced (see figure).

Red-pericarped At85-1 had medium tolerance for acidic soils, low shattering, and higher grain weight (25-26 g/1000 seeds). It had little tolerance for submerged condition and was susceptible to BPH, thrips, and ShB. Its short height (81-87 cm) made the microenvironment suitable for pests and diseases.

After eight seasons, farmers are again adopting BW272-3, which is moderately